

long-term affirmative change toward peace.

Rinker admits that the three organizations represent only a fraction of the vast diversity of the anticaste network. They symbolize the ideological, organizational, and geographical diversity within the anticaste movement and act as a representative sample. The author urges scholars of caste to focus on the stories narrated by social movement activists. Speech and storytelling are forms of direct action and the foundation of the activists' vision for social change.

Identity, rights, and awareness are created through a combination of narrative construction of meaning and material collective action, as well as the contextual relativism of stories and rights as universal values. Rinker contends that discursively focused work should not come from academics and theorists like himself, who sit on the periphery, but rather from within the activist community—only this can shape the discourse. He refers here to what peacebuilding expert John Paul Lederach calls the “elicitive model.”

Rinker's remarkable study not only explores the differences *between* the three organizations but also the differences *within* each. He draws attention to TBMSG's creation of Buddhist self-esteem and how it is conflated with a Hindu majority *other*. Rinker observes that BAMCEF's work on intercaste connections among the underprivileged still maintains a deep gap between the powerful and the weak. He also notes that PVCHR is moving away from a caste- and religion-based insider/outsider bifurcation to a human-centred cosmopolitan values approach. The key to realizing long-term structural change, Rinker argues, is paying critical attention to the differences within the anticaste movements and embracing them as a resource rather than perceiving them as constraints. Toward that end, the author gives a clarion call for collaboration and coalescence, challenging not only the marginalized but also the privileged to creatively change the system of oppression.

One aspect that might have improved Rinker's study would have been a discussion of other anticaste movements. Examples of these include Periyar's historical role and the efforts of the Dravidian governments in Tamil Nadu; Marxist governments in Kerala empowering the marginalized; the appointment of Hindu priests belonging to downtrodden communities including Dalits in both states; and the Bahujan Samaj Party's success in Uttar Pradesh. Although the Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh (RSS) is portrayed as a hegemonic opponent to Dalit empowerment, the RSS has

worked tirelessly to uplift members of the Dalit community for decades through its Seva Bharati (Service to India) and Samajik Samarasta Manch (Social Harmony Platform) branches. Also, the Vishwa Hindu Parishad has trained thousands of Dalit priests.

Rinker's work underscores the indispensability of education as an empowering tool for Dalits—a reality that is emphasized as a critical universal in the resistance identity of the three organizations. This is reiterated by a quote from Dr. B.R. Ambedkar: “The backward classes have come to realize that after all education is the greatest material benefit for which they can fight ... that without education [their] existence is not safe” (p. 12). Although caste discrimination continues in India, this book is an asset to scholars, practitioners, activists, and politicians working to mitigate caste hierarchy. Within that context, this book is a milestone in peace studies.

Durgesh Kasbekar

*Member of the Executive Committee, Religion
in International Relation Section*

International Studies Association (ISA)

Balihar Sanghera and Elmira Satybaldieva. *Rentier Capitalism and Its Discontents: Power, Morality and Resistance in Central Asia*. Cambridge, UK: Open Book Publishers, 2020. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, 2021. ISBN 9783-030-76302-2 (hardcover); 978-3-030-76303-9 (e-book). Pp. xxiii + 321.

What one factor might explain the different phenomena of chaotic urbanization, ecological degradation, chronic social inequality, the emergence of conflict-prone societies, and the rise and consolidation of authoritarian, oligarchic, and plutocratic regimes in Central Asia and the greater Eurasian region? A critical analysis of rentier capitalism is needed to understand holistically the above-mentioned and many other phenomena.

Rentier Capitalism and Its Discontents, by Balihar Sanghera and Elmira Satybaldieva, provides just such an analysis, and one that many have

anticipated. This book offers a comprehensive, coherent, justice-oriented examination of the social, economic, and political processes that unfolded in the post-Soviet area following the collapse of the Soviet system, specifically in Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan.

To explore the role that rentier capitalism has played in shaping the social forces underlying the multidimensional crisis wrought on humankind (ranging from systemic social and economic inequalities and indebtedness to political authoritarianism and destruction of natural habitat) and to understand the nature of poverty, hardship, and deprivation among poor and working-class groups, the authors use a retroductive research strategy within a wider Southern perspective. This perspective and approach together inform the humanistic, non-hegemonic (“close to the real people here and everywhere”), and emancipatory aspects of this research, distinguishing it from so-called conventional research done using purely positivistic approaches and Northern- and Western-centric perspectives. The authors back their analyses and findings with extensive fieldwork and years of empirical and practical experience in the post-socialist context.

The critical analysis of fictitious commodities is crucial for understanding the underlying reasons and factors behind today’s multidimensional crisis—this is what makes the book highly valuable to scholars of political economy, sociology, political science, economics, philosophy, Central Asian studies, and many other fields. Sanghera and Satybaldieva follow the epistemology formulated by scholars like Andrew Sayer,¹ holding that social scientists cannot avoid making evaluations in terms of justice and fairness. It is unfortunate that many normative theorists are still ghettoized in political theory and moral philosophy, while economists, political scientists, sociologists, and others show little interest in normative thought. Sanghera and Satybaldieva bring together largely overlooked arguments to offer a coherent analysis of what creates the highly exploitative and unjust economic and political system in post-socialist countries.

The authors show how “disembedding” from the social needs economy—which is the key characteristic and aim of rentier capitalism—not only commodifies almost all aspects of human life but also annihilates social justice, the judicial system, and life itself. Economic values are seen as the preeminent values; in contrast, social and public interests determined by social and political processes are never regarded as primary concerns by

rentier capitalism. In line with the analyses of Karl Polanyi, who has made the most potent and systematic critique of free-market ideas and practices in recent history, the authors show how rentier capitalism and its local adaptations in Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan lead to exclusion, rightlessness, and despair.

Sanghera and Satybaldieva analyze the extensions of rentier capitalism in Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan in different sectors such as the financial sector, including microfinance organizations, which alongside banks have become predatory institutions; the property development and real estate sector; and the extraction sector and natural resources, including the role of transnational capital and ensuing environmental degradation. They demonstrate how privatization and the turning of money, land, and labour (as well as knowledge) into fictitious commodities creates the immense political capital of the rich, which represents a victory for plutocracy over democracy (p. 45). The authors explore not just the ubiquitous indebtedness of the population, neoliberal property, and land-owning regimes that have dispossessed ordinary people, but also grassroots movements for housing and land rights, anti-debt protest groups, and their activities.

Overall, this book is about structural violence and “positive peace.” Structural violence, following Johan Galtung, refers to the systemic, political, and social factors that create and sustain inequality. Structural violence is synonymous with social injustice.² In contrast to “negative peace,” which is about the absence of direct violence, “positive peace” refers to the absence of structural violence.³ Neither freedom nor peace can be institutionalized under rentier capitalism or, more generally, under an unregulated market or “disembedded” from the social needs economy. Hence, a critical analysis of rentier neoliberal capitalism is necessary to understand the value of social justice, which is essential to achieving positive peace. Both social justice and positive peace are structural and embedded in economic and social relations. It is impossible to overcome social and political violence without building social justice and fighting against rentier capitalism. This book emphasizes the need to transcend the so-called self-regulating market, which has become embodied in rentier capitalism, by consciously subordinating it to democratic society. Rather than pursuing the incessant accumulation of capital, socially oriented democratic alternatives built around human well-being, a care for life, and ecological protection are needed. This is what the protest groups and movements in Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, which are

analyzed by Sanghera and Satybaldieva, demand.

The only thing I would have suggested to the authors was to devote more attention to the universality and indivisibility of human rights. The penetration of rentier neoliberal capitalism into human rights has seriously diminished the emancipatory potential as well as the normative and moral power of human rights.

It is quite meaningful to write this review in the aftermath of the January 2022 protests in Kazakhstan, which were unprecedentedly large for the entire Eurasian region, and which pushed the country to political and social transformations that had been awaited for decades. January's societal upheaval in Kazakhstan was caused by the combination of different factors generated by rentier capitalism, which was operating symbiotically with the plutocratic authoritarian Kazakhstani regime.

Overall, I want to congratulate the authors, the readership, and the ordinary people of Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan—who represent the billions around the world who struggle for their dignity, social justice, and peace—on the publication of this brilliant book, which is also a trailblazer for post-socialist and post-Soviet studies.

Galym Zhussipbek

Suleyman Demirel atindagi Universitet

ENDNOTES

- 1 Andrew Sayer, "Welfare and Moral Economy," *Ethics and Social Welfare* 12, no. 1 (2018): 20–33
- 2 Johan Galtung, "Violence, Peace, and Peace Research," *Journal of Peace Research* 6, no. 3 (1969): 171.
- 3 Stephen Gibson, "Discursive Psychology and Peace Psychology," in *Discourse, Peace, and Conflict*, ed. Stephen Gibson (Cham: Springer, 2018), 4.